

Tolerability of COVID-19 mRNA vaccine in patients with postural tachycardia syndrome

Date: __/__/____

Sheet filled out by: _____

Participant number: ____

Inclusion criteria checklist

Yes

No

Patient diagnosed with neuropathic POTS	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Received two COVID-19 mRNA vaccinations for ≥ 1 month; or recovered from COVID-19 infection for ≥ 1 month	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Informed consent available	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Exclusion criteria checklist

Yes

No

Age: <18 years und >60 years	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Demographic data

COVID-19 infection undergone? Yes No

Age:

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Sex:

- male
 female

Side effects of vaccinations:

	First vaccination	Second vaccination
	Date: _____	Date: _____
	Vaccine: <input type="checkbox"/> Moderna <input type="checkbox"/> Pfizer	Vaccine: <input type="checkbox"/> Moderna <input type="checkbox"/> Pfizer
	Incapacity to work: _____ days	Incapacity to work: _____ days
Side effect	Severity and duration	Severity and duration
Fever	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Shivering	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Fatigue	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Headache	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Joint pain	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Muscle pain	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Nausea	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Emesis	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Diarrhea	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Reaction at injection site: pain	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days
Reaction at injection site: swelling and cutaneous reaction	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No _____ days

Change in POTS symptoms after vaccinations:

	First vaccination	Second vaccination
	Adjustment of treatment: -----	Adjustment of treatment: -----
	Incapacity to work: ----- days	Incapacity to work: ----- days
Symptom	Severity and duration	Severity and duration
Dizziness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Nausea	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Weakness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Palpitations	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Lightheadedness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Tremulousness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Blurred vision	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Concentration difficulties	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Memory difficulties	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Orthostatic leg and/or arm pain	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Gastrointestinal symptoms	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Sleep disturbances	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Restless legs syndrom	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days
Orthostatic headache	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No ----- days

Symptoms of COVID-19 infection:

	<p>COVID-19 infection</p> <p>Date: _____</p> <p>Duration: _____</p> <p>Hospitalization (Duration): _____</p> <p>Adjustment of treatment: _____</p> <p>Incapacity to work: _____ days</p>
Side effect	Severity and duration
Fever	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe _____ days
Shivering	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe _____ days
Fatigue	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe _____ days
Headache	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe _____ days
Joint pain	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe _____ days
Muscle pain	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe _____ days
Nausea	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe _____ days
Emesis	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe _____ days

Diarrhea	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe ----- days
Coughing	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe ----- days
Sore thorat	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe ----- days
Rhinorrhea	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe ----- days
Breathlessness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe ----- days
Loss of taste	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe ----- days
Loss of smell	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe ----- days
Chest pain	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe ----- days

Change in POTS symptoms after COVID-19 infection:

	<p>COVID-19 infection</p> <p>Adjustment of treatment:</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Incapacity to work:</p> <p>----- Tage</p>
Symptom	Severity and duration
Dizziness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe <p>----- days</p>
Nausea	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe <p>----- days</p>
Weakness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe <p>----- days</p>
Palpitations	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe <p>----- days</p>
Lightheadedness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe <p>----- days</p>
Tremulousness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe <p>----- days</p>
Blurred vision	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe <p>----- days</p>
Concentration difficulties	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe <p>----- days</p>
Memory difficulties	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe <p>----- days</p>
Orthostatic leg and/or arm pain	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe

	<p>----- days</p>
Gastrointestinal symptoms	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe</p> <p>----- days</p>
Sleep disturbances	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe</p> <p>----- days</p>
Restless legs syndrome	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe</p> <p>----- days</p>
Orthostatic headache	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Mild <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Severe</p> <p>----- days</p>